

Steklov Activations: Piecewise-Polynomial Gates with Compact Support and Tunable Sparsity

Aleksandr Masalskikh
alex@masalskikh.com

April 7, 2026

Abstract

We introduce *Steklov activations*, a family of piecewise-polynomial activation functions derived from antiderivatives of Steklov summation kernels in approximation theory. Parameterized by order r (smoothness) and scale α (transition width), they produce exact zero output and exact zero gradient outside a compact support of width $r\alpha$. The third-order variant at $\alpha=2$ closely approximates GELU (sup error < 0.0091); at $r=1$ and $\alpha=6$, the activation is exactly HardSwish.

We evaluate across three CNN architectures and three transformer architectures (105M–354M parameters, up to 5 seeds). On image classification, Steklov $\alpha=0.8$ achieves the highest accuracy on all four benchmarks (MNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100 on ResNet-18 and WideResNet-28-10), improving over GELU by 0.43–0.51 pp. On GPT-2 Small (124M, 5 seeds), Steklov achieves the lowest mean perplexity (22.39 ± 0.69 vs GELU 22.97 ± 0.47), though the gap is not statistically significant ($p = 0.30$). On GPT-2 Medium (354M, 3–4 seeds), Steklov $\alpha=2.0$ matches GELU closely (22.69 ± 0.38 vs 22.56 ± 0.29). On a 105M LLaMA-style model (RMSNorm, RoPE, 3 seeds), all Steklov variants achieve lower mean perplexity than SiLU, with the learnable variant reducing perplexity by 2.0%. At $\alpha \leq 0.1$ (single seed), 87–90% of MLP activations are exactly zero per token, yet perplexity remains better than dense SiLU. Parameter-matched SwiGLU ($d_{\text{ff}}=2048$, 124M, 3 seeds) underperforms both GELU and Steklov, suggesting that, in this setup, the standard-width SwiGLU advantage over GELU is not preserved under parameter matching.

The compact support induces two architecture-dependent forms of sparsity. On GPT-2, 7–12% of neurons become *permanently dead* (inactive on $>99.9\%$ of tokens) and can be structurally pruned with +0.05 to +0.23 PPL cost, while matched-rate magnitude pruning performs dramatically worse in our experiments ($> 10^5$ PPL). After structural pruning, a Triton kernel delivers a 3–5% inference speedup over unpruned GELU in our benchmark setting.

On LLaMA, no neurons die permanently, but the per-token zeros naturally produce 98–99% compliance with NVIDIA’s 2:4 structured sparsity format; enforcing the hardware pattern costs <2 PPL, compared to +25.9 for SiLU. Both sparsity forms are stable across the tested data splits (Jaccard > 0.99) and across distributions (Jaccard > 0.97 at the $\geq 99\%$ inactivity threshold). Downstream benchmarks (ARC-Easy, HellaSwag, LAMBADA, PIQA, WinoGrande) show no evidence of degradation from sparsity or pruning beyond what perplexity predicts.

1 Introduction

Activation functions are among the simplest components of neural network architectures, yet their choice has outsized impact on training dynamics, representational capacity, and inference efficiency. The progression from sigmoid to ReLU [13] to GELU [10] to SiLU/Swish [11, 12] and SwiGLU [19] reflects a gradual shift toward smooth, gated activations. But these functions all share a property that limits their practical exploitation: their tails decay exponentially but never reach exactly zero.

A neuron with a large negative input under GELU or SiLU produces an output that is extremely small but nonzero, and receives a correspondingly small but nonzero gradient. This makes it difficult to determine which neurons are “unused” and could be safely removed.

In this work, we introduce a family of activation functions that break this pattern. The *Steklov activations* are piecewise-polynomial gates derived from the Steklov summation kernels of approximation theory [1]. Their key property is *compact support*: the gate is exactly zero below a finite threshold and exactly one above another, with a smooth polynomial transition in between. Neurons outside the support produce mathematically exact zero output and receive exactly zero gradient (Figure 2).

The family is parameterized by two quantities: order r , which controls the polynomial degree and smoothness (C^{r-1}), and scale α , which controls the width of the transition region. At $r=3$ and $\alpha=2$, the activation closely approximates GELU (sup error < 0.0091 , Figure 3); at $r=1$ and $\alpha=6$, it is exactly HardSwish [15]. The parameter α acts as a continuous sparsity knob: decreasing α narrows the support, pushing more neurons into the inactive region (Figure 4b).

We evaluate Steklov activations across five architectures (LeNet-5, ResNet-18, WideResNet-28-10, GPT-2 (124M and 354M), and a LLaMA-style decoder (105M)) and find that they are competitive with or improve upon GELU and SiLU across both vision and language tasks while providing tunable activation sparsity absent in all standard activations. The compact support induces two distinct forms of sparsity depending on architecture: *structural* sparsity (permanently dead neurons, exploitable through static pruning) and *dynamic* sparsity (per-token zeros, exploitable through N:M hardware patterns). On GPT-2, 7–12% of neurons become permanently dead and can be pruned with negligible quality loss. On LLaMA with very small α (≤ 0.1), 87–90% of activations are zero per token, achieving 98–99% natural 2:4 structured sparsity compliance. Both forms are stable across seeds, data splits, and distributions.

2 Steklov Activation Formulation

2.1 From Approximation Theory to Activation Functions

Let a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be integrable on any finite interval, for $(r - 1) \in \mathbb{N}, h > 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$ we set

$$S_{1,h}(f, x) = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} f(x+t)dt,$$

$$S_{r,h}(f) = S_{1,h}(S_{r-1,h}(f)).$$

The functions $S_{r,h}$ are referred to as Steklov functions of order r . Their systematic application in approximation theory was first undertaken by N. I. Akhiezer ([2, 3, 4]).

The Steklov functions admit a representation as a convolution

$$S_{h,r}(f, x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x+ht)\psi_r(t)dt, \tag{1}$$

where $\psi_r = \psi_1 * \dots * \psi_1$ (r times). The function ψ_r is called the *Steklov kernel* of order r . Since ψ_r is the r -fold convolution of ψ_1 , it vanishes outside the interval $[-r/2, r/2]$. Hence ψ_r is a compactly supported positive kernel. Detailed properties and more information about Steklov kernels you can find in [1]. Owing to their properties, these kernels are well suited for the construction of various approximation operators and algorithms based on them ([5, 8, 9, 7]).

The kernel ψ_r of order r is the centered cardinal B-spline of order $r - 1$:

$$\psi_r(t) = \frac{1}{(r-1)!} \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} \left(t + \frac{r}{2} - k\right)_+^{r-1}, \quad (2)$$

where $(x)_+ = \max(0, x)$ is the truncated power. Each ψ_r is non-negative, symmetric, normalized ($\int \psi_r = 1$), supported on $[-r/2, r/2]$, and C^{r-2} -smooth. The first three are the box function ($r=1$), triangular hat ($r=2$), and quadratic B-spline ($r=3$).

Definition 1 (Steklov sigmoid). *The Steklov sigmoid of order r with scale $\alpha > 0$ is*

$$\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = \frac{1}{r!} \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha} + \frac{r}{2} - k\right)_+^r. \quad (3)$$

This is the antiderivative $1 - \Phi_r(x/\alpha)$ of the kernel, where $\Phi_r(u) = \int_u^\infty \psi_r(t) dt$. Since ψ_r has finite support, $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 0$ for $x \leq -r\alpha/2$ and $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 1$ for $x \geq r\alpha/2$, with a C^{r-1} piecewise-polynomial transition of degree r in between (Proposition 2). The sigmoid is monotone, symmetric ($\sigma_S(x) + \sigma_S(-x) = 1$), and passes through $1/2$ at $x = 0$ (Figure 1).

Figure 1: (a) Steklov sigmoids $\sigma_S^{(r)}$ for orders 1–3 with their support boundaries (dashed). Higher order yields wider support and smoother transition. (b) The order-3 Steklov sigmoid at $\alpha=2$ (pink) compared with the Gaussian CDF (blue dashed) and logistic sigmoid (purple dotted). Outside the compact support $[-3, 3]$, the Steklov sigmoid is exactly 0 or 1.

Definition 2 (SteklovSiLU). *The SteklovSiLU activation is $\text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) = x \cdot \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha)$.*

For practical implementation, the order-3 closed form is:

$$\text{SteklovSiLU}_3(x; \alpha) = x \cdot \begin{cases} 0 & u \leq -\frac{3}{2} \\ \frac{1}{6}(u + \frac{3}{2})^3 & -\frac{3}{2} < u \leq -\frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{4}u - \frac{1}{3}u^3 & -\frac{1}{2} < u \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ 1 - \frac{1}{6}(\frac{3}{2} - u)^3 & \frac{1}{2} < u < \frac{3}{2} \\ 1 & u \geq \frac{3}{2} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $u = x/\alpha$. This requires only multiply-add operations and requires no transcendental functions. Order 1 gives $x \cdot \text{clamp}(u + 1/2, 0, 1)$, which is exactly HardSwish [15] at $\alpha = 6$ (Proposition 3).

Figure 2: SteklovSiLU compared with standard activation functions. At $\alpha=2.0$ (pink), the activation closely tracks GELU (blue). At $\alpha=0.8$ (amber), the support narrows to $[-1.2, 1.2]$ and the activation is exactly zero for all $x < -1.2$. HardSwish (green dashed) is exactly $\text{SteklovSiLU}_1(x; \alpha=6)$.

2.2 Relationship to GELU

Proposition 1 (GELU approximation). $\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |\text{SteklovSiLU}_3(x; 2) - \text{GELU}(x)| < 0.0091$.

Proof. Appendix A. The bound is tight, achieved at $|x| \approx 2.48$ (confirmed on a 10^5 -point grid with scalar optimization). Outside $[-3, 3]$, the Steklov sigmoid is exactly 0 or 1 while the Gaussian CDF is exponentially close, so the product-with- x error decays rapidly. Inside $[-3, 3]$, both sigmoids are smooth and close, with the maximum product error occurring where $|x|$ is moderately large and the sigmoid difference is still non-negligible.

As $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, SteklovSiLU converges pointwise to ReLU for $x \neq 0$; as $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, it converges to $x/2$ (Proposition 5). The parameter α thus interpolates continuously between a hard threshold and a linear scaling, with the GELU-like regime at $\alpha \approx 2$.

2.3 The α Parameter as a Sparsity Knob

For a pre-activation z entering the activation, define: **inactive** ($z < -r\alpha/2$, output = 0, gradient = 0), **active** ($|z| \leq r\alpha/2$, polynomial transition), **linear** ($z > r\alpha/2$, output = z , gradient = 1). The inactive and linear classifications are exact, not approximate. Decreasing α narrows the support, pushing more of the pre-activation distribution into the inactive region. This creates a direct, predictable relationship between α and the fraction of inactive neurons.

Figure 3: Pointwise error $\text{SteklovSiLU}_3(x; 2) - \text{GELU}(x)$. The supremum < 0.0091 is achieved at $|x| \approx 2.48$ (red dot). Outside the support $[-3, 3]$ (dashed lines), the Steklov activation is exactly 0 or x , while GELU has exponentially small but nonzero tails.

2.4 Learnable α

Rather than fixing α as a hyperparameter, it can be treated as a trainable parameter optimized jointly with the network weights. Since the Steklov sigmoid is differentiable with respect to α , gradients flow through α naturally. In practice, we initialize a single scalar α shared across all layers with the same optimizer settings. A single global α performs comparably to per-layer α (within 0.18 PPL on GPT-2 Small, 3 seeds).

The converged α is architecture-dependent: ~ 2.24 on GPT-2, ~ 1.73 on LLaMA, and ~ 0.2 on CIFAR CNNs. Ablations on GPT-2 Small show that this preference is robust: neither removing bias from linear layers nor replacing LayerNorm with RMSNorm significantly changes the converged value ($\alpha \approx 2.16$ – 2.29 across all variants, 3 seeds each). Initialization sensitivity is low: starting α at 0.5–4.0 yields final PPL within 0.21, though the converged α retains some memory of initialization (1.79–2.93), suggesting a shallow loss landscape with many near-optimal points.

2.5 Implementation

The piecewise polynomial uses only `torch.where` and standard arithmetic, which `torch.compile` fuses automatically into surrounding linear layers. In a full GPT-2 Small training step, this adds 2% overhead (133.8 ms vs 130.7 ms). A fused Triton kernel eliminates remaining overhead: in our benchmarks, Steklov inference matches GELU latency within 1–2% at the tested batch sizes. After structural pruning (permanently removing inactive neurons and shrinking weight matrices), Steklov + Triton is 3–5% faster than unpruned GELU in the same setting.

3 Experiments

We evaluate on image classification (MNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100) and language modeling (GPT-2 Small 124M, GPT-2 Medium 354M, LLaMA-style 105M). All experiments use the order-3 Steklov kernel ($r=3$), which provides C^2 smoothness at the support boundaries and closely approximates GELU at $\alpha=2$ (Proposition 4). We choose $r=3$ as the lowest order that yields a smooth, non-piecewise-linear gate while requiring only multiply-add arithmetic (Eq. 4). Classification: 5 seeds;

Figure 4: (a) SteklovSiLU₃ at $\alpha=2$ closely matches GELU and SiLU. (b) Decreasing α from 2.0 to 0.5 progressively narrows the support and expands the zero-output region, approaching ReLU. (c) Order comparison at $\alpha=2$: higher order yields smoother transitions. Steklov₁($\alpha=6$) overlaps exactly with HardSwish (dashed).

language modeling: 3–5 seeds. Full hyperparameters in Appendix.

3.1 Vision: MNIST, CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100

Before testing on language models, we verify that Steklov activations perform at least as well as standard nonlinearities on image classification, where GELU and SiLU are established baselines. If the activation degrades accuracy, there is no reason to proceed to more expensive transformer experiments. We test three architectures: LeNet-5 on MNIST, ResNet-18 on CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100, and WideResNet-28-10 on CIFAR-100 (all 5 seeds).

Table 1: Best test accuracy (% , mean \pm std, 5 seeds) across vision benchmarks.

Activation	MNIST	CIFAR-10	C-100 (R18)	C-100 (WRN)
GELU	98.40 \pm 0.07	94.92 \pm 0.07	78.54 \pm 0.28	80.72 \pm 0.20
SiLU	98.34 \pm 0.05	94.31 \pm 0.08	77.22 \pm 0.19	78.58 \pm 0.19
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	98.33 \pm 0.04	94.84 \pm 0.08	78.44 \pm 0.19	80.52 \pm 0.11
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	98.43 \pm 0.10	95.43 \pm 0.12	78.97 \pm 0.17	81.17 \pm 0.24
Stek learned	98.33 \pm 0.04	95.33 \pm 0.21	78.67 \pm 0.37	80.35 \pm 0.15

Steklov $\alpha = 0.8$ achieves the highest accuracy on all four benchmarks (Table 1, Figure 5), improving over GELU by +0.51 pp on CIFAR-10, +0.43 pp on CIFAR-100 ResNet-18, and +0.45 pp on CIFAR-100 WideResNet-28-10. Steklov $\alpha=2.0$ closely tracks GELU (within 0.2 pp), consistent with the approximation bound. The learnable variant converges to $\alpha \approx 0.2$ on CNNs, confirming that these architectures prefer a narrow, ReLU-like transition.

Takeaway. Steklov activations are competitive with and often improve over GELU and SiLU on all tested vision benchmarks. The compact support does not hurt representation quality; if anything, the implicit sparsity at $\alpha=0.8$ acts as a beneficial regularizer on these tasks.

Figure 5: Best test accuracy across four vision benchmarks (5 seeds, error bars ± 1 std). Stek $\alpha=0.8$ achieves the highest accuracy on every benchmark.

3.2 GPT-2 Small (124M)

Two questions motivate this experiment. First, we test whether Steklov can replace GELU in a transformer language model without quality loss. Second, SwiGLU is widely believed to outperform GELU, but SwiGLU uses a third weight matrix that adds 23% more parameters; we investigate whether the advantage comes from the gating mechanism or simply from having more parameters. We test at 124M scale with 5 seeds.

Table 2: GPT-2 Small, WikiText-103, 25K steps. Fair SwiGLU uses $d_{\text{ff}} = 2048$ to match 124M. [†]Single-run reference.

Activation	Params	d_{ff}	PPL (mean \pm std)	Seeds	Speed
GELU	124M	3072	22.97 \pm 0.47	5	1.00 \times
Stek learned	124M	3072	22.39 \pm 0.69	5	1.02 \times
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	124M	3072	22.73 \pm 0.52	5	1.02 \times
SwiGLU (fair)	124M	2048	23.25 \pm 0.25	3	1.07 \times
SwiGLU (std) [†]	152M	3072	22.65	1	$\sim 1.07\times$

Stek learned achieves the lowest mean PPL (Table 2), though the gap to GELU is not statistically significant at this sample size (Cohen’s $d = 0.99$, $p = 0.30$). Standard SwiGLU (22.65 at 152M) appears to beat GELU, but SwiGLU (fair) at matched parameters ($d_{\text{ff}}=2048$, 124M) scores 23.25, worse than both GELU and Steklov. A 9-point α sweep maps the sparsity–quality frontier: 25% to 85% inactivity costs only +0.30 PPL. Multi-seed replication confirms inactivity variance $\leq 0.8\%$ std.

Takeaway. Steklov is a viable GELU replacement at 124M scale. In this setup, the advantage of standard-width SwiGLU over GELU is not preserved under parameter matching.

3.3 GPT-2 Medium (354M)

The GELU approximation (Proposition 4) predicts that Steklov $\alpha = 2.0$ should be a drop-in replacement at any scale. We test this at 354M parameters, 2.9 \times larger, and additionally test whether the sparsity–quality tradeoff holds: whether $\alpha = 0.8$ still produces high inactivity at a modest PPL cost.

Table 3: GPT-2 Medium, OpenWebText, 50K steps. One GELU seed (42) diverged at step ~ 7500 .

Config	PPL (mean \pm std)	Seeds	Inactive%	σ_z
GELU	22.56 \pm 0.29	3	21.0%	1.359
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	22.69 \pm 0.38	4	19.5%	1.283
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	22.90 \pm 0.30	3	58.4%	1.014

Steklov $\alpha=2.0$ remains close to GELU, with a difference small relative to the reported seed variability (+0.13 PPL, Table 3), supporting the approximation at scale. At $\alpha=0.8$, 58% of activations fall in the inactive region per token for only +1.5% PPL cost. Inactivity is stable across seeds (std $< 1\%$). Notably, the GELU seed that diverged at step 7500 converged under Steklov at the same seed, consistent with a possible stability benefit from compact support.

Table 4: Downstream benchmarks, GPT-2 Medium (mean over 2 seeds). All scores are accuracy (%).

Config	HellaSwag	LAMBADA acc	LAMBADA ppl	ARC-Easy
GELU	27.80	24.50	38.3	36.97
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	27.66	24.66	38.0	36.30
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	27.55	24.77	38.1	36.47

Downstream scores track perplexity (Table 4). At 58% inactivity, all metrics degrade by $< 0.5\%$ absolute vs GELU.

Takeaway. The GELU approximation holds at 354M. The sparsity–quality tradeoff scales: the $\alpha \rightarrow$ inactivity mapping is consistent between 124M and 354M, and the PPL cost remains modest. Downstream tasks show no evidence of quality degradation beyond what PPL predicts.

3.4 LLaMA-Style (105M)

GPT-2 uses LayerNorm, learned positional embeddings, and bias in all linear layers. Modern LLMs (Llama, Mistral, Gemma) use a different recipe: RMSNorm, rotary embeddings (RoPE), no bias, and SiLU instead of GELU. We test whether the Steklov activation transfers to this different architectural context. We train a ~ 105 M LLaMA-style model (12 layers, $d_{\text{ff}}=2048$, two-matrix MLP) on OpenWebText for 25K steps.

All Steklov variants achieve lower mean PPL than SiLU (Table 5), and the ordering is consistent across all 3 seeds. The learnable variant converges to $\alpha \approx 1.73$, between the GELU-like ($\alpha=2$) and high-sparsity ($\alpha=0.8$) regimes. A notable result appears in the bottom half of the table: at $\alpha=0.005$, 90% of MLP activations are in the zero-output region on every forward pass, yet PPL (30.47) is better than SiLU (31.43). On GPT-2 Small, training is stable down to $\alpha=0.1$ but diverges at $\alpha=0.05$; LLaMA tolerates much narrower support widths.

Takeaway. Steklov transfers to LLaMA-style architectures without modification. The small- α results ($\alpha \leq 0.1$) show that, in this 105M LLaMA-style setup, the model remains competitive with SiLU even when 87–90% of MLP activations are exactly zero per token. This is the foundation for the N:M hardware sparsity results in Section 3.8.

Table 5: LLaMA-style ($\sim 105\text{M}$), OpenWebText, 25K steps. SwiGLU uses three-matrix MLP ($\sim 124\text{M}$). [†]Single-run reference.

Activation	Params	PPL (mean \pm std)	Seeds	Inactive%
SiLU	$\sim 105\text{M}$	31.43 ± 0.87	3	17.1%
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.88 ± 0.89	3	3.4%
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.99 ± 0.88	3	28.0%
Stek learned	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.79 ± 0.90	3	6.5%
SwiGLU (ref) [†]	$\sim 124\text{M}$	32.66	1	—
Stek $\alpha=0.1$	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.57	1	87.2%
Stek $\alpha=0.05$	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.47	1	88.9%
Stek $\alpha=0.005$	$\sim 105\text{M}$	30.47	1	90.2%

3.5 Downstream Benchmarks

Perplexity measures how well a model predicts the next token, but it does not guarantee that higher-level capabilities (reasoning, commonsense, factual recall) are preserved. A model could improve PPL by memorizing surface statistics while losing task-relevant representations. We evaluate on five standard benchmarks: ARC-Easy [27] (grade-school science questions), HellaSwag [28] (commonsense sentence completion), LAMBADA [29] (long-range cloze prediction), PIQA [30] (physical intuition), and WinoGrande [31] (pronoun resolution). All evaluations are 0-shot via lm-evaluation-harness.

Table 6: Downstream evaluation, GPT-2 Small 124M, α sweep (single seed). All scores accuracy (%).

Config	ARC-E	HellaS.	LAMB.	PIQA	WinoG.	Mean
GELU	33.25	25.74	9.06	52.77	51.07	34.38
Stek $\alpha=0.5$	31.44	25.98	8.46	52.12	50.20	33.64
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	32.79	26.00	9.31	52.18	50.43	34.14
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	33.75	25.99	9.31	54.03	50.04	34.63
Stek $\alpha=0.8$ (pruned)	32.74	26.00	9.35	52.18	50.36	34.13

On GPT-2 Small (Table 6), all Steklov configurations are within 1.2% of GELU across all five benchmarks. The $\alpha=2.0$ variant slightly exceeds GELU in mean score (34.63 vs 34.38). Pruning 7.6% of neurons at $\alpha=0.8$ changes the mean score by 0.01. Pruning changes the mean downstream score by only 0.01 in this run.

Table 7: Downstream evaluation, LLaMA-style 105M (single seed). All scores are accuracy (%).

Config	ARC-E	HellaS.	LAMB.	PIQA	WinoG.	Mean
SiLU	35.61	26.28	19.31	57.34	49.80	37.67
Stek $\alpha=2.0$	36.78	26.63	20.51	57.78	50.36	38.41
Stek learned	35.31	26.24	20.43	57.73	52.57	38.46
Stek $\alpha=0.05$	36.32	26.33	18.86	57.18	52.17	38.17
Stek $\alpha=0.005$	35.52	26.64	19.15	56.58	52.09	38.00

On LLaMA (Table 7), at 89% per-token activation sparsity ($\alpha=0.05$), the mean score is 38.17 vs SiLU’s 37.67, with no measurable degradation despite 9 out of 10 MLP activations being identically zero per token.

Takeaway. Neither activation sparsity nor structural pruning degrades downstream task performance beyond what perplexity predicts. The compact support does not selectively damage any task-relevant capability.

3.6 Sparsity Stability

For inactivity-based pruning to be practical, the set of inactive neurons must be a property of the *trained weights*, not of the particular data used to profile them. If different evaluation datasets identified different neurons as inactive, one would need to re-profile for every deployment domain, making pruning fragile and impractical. We test this with three increasingly stringent checks.

Within-distribution stability. We profile inactivity on three non-overlapping shards of WikiText-103 (validation, training start, training offset 50M tokens). Global inactivity rates vary by at most $\pm 0.17\%$ across shards (Table 8). The set of neurons exceeding the 99% inactivity threshold has Jaccard overlap >0.99 for $\alpha \leq 0.8$, meaning virtually the same neurons are identified as inactive regardless of which shard is used for profiling.

Table 8: Within-distribution stability: three non-overlapping WikiText-103 shards (GPT-2 Small).

Config	Inactivity range across shards	Jaccard ($>99\%$)	Jaccard ($>99.9\%$)
$\alpha=2.0$	$\pm 0.12\%$	>0.97	>0.97
$\alpha=0.8$	$\pm 0.17\%$	>0.99	>0.99
$\alpha=0.5$	$\pm 0.09\%$	>0.99	>0.99

Cross-distribution stability. A stronger test: we profile GPT-2 Small models *trained* on WikiText-103 for inactivity on OpenWebText, a different corpus with different domain composition, vocabulary distribution, and document length. If the inactive neuron set were an artifact of the training data, it would change substantially.

Table 9: Cross-distribution stability: models trained on WikiText-103, profiled on OpenWebText.

Config	Global inactivity		Jaccard overlap of inactive set		
	WT-103	OWT	$>95\%$	$>99\%$	$>99.9\%$
$\alpha=0.8$	64.07%	65.61%	0.928	0.978	0.978
$\alpha=0.5$	83.21%	83.60%	0.599	0.974	0.984

At the conservative thresholds used for pruning ($\geq 99\%$), the same neurons are inactive on both datasets: Jaccard overlap is 0.978 for $\alpha=0.8$ and 0.974–0.984 for $\alpha=0.5$ (Table 9). At the looser 95% threshold, Jaccard drops to 0.60 for $\alpha=0.5$: marginal neurons near the boundary are distribution-sensitive. The 99.9% pruning threshold avoids this sensitivity.

Per-layer stability. The layerwise inactivity profile is also preserved across distributions. Table 10 shows the per-layer comparison for $\alpha=0.8$. The characteristic pattern (layer 1 near-saturated at 94%, middle layers 50–70%, output layer recovering to 65%) appears identically on both datasets, with per-layer differences typically below 3 pp.

Table 10: Per-layer inactivity (%), $\alpha=0.8$, GPT-2 Small. Same model, different data.

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
WT-103	15.8	94.3	74.5	46.2	50.0	56.6	63.8	70.0	76.0	78.9	77.4	65.2
OWT	12.5	94.1	74.7	47.6	52.5	61.2	71.6	74.9	79.1	79.8	75.0	64.3
Δ (pp)	-3.4	-0.2	+0.2	+1.4	+2.5	+4.6	+7.8	+4.9	+3.1	+0.9	-2.4	-0.9

Takeaway. Pruning is a one-time operation: profile inactivity on a representative calibration set, remove neurons above the 99.9% threshold, and deploy. The pruned model does not need to be re-calibrated for different domains.

3.7 Dynamic vs Structural Sparsity

Not all zeros are created equal. A neuron that outputs zero for *this particular token* but fires on others is *dynamically sparse* and cannot be removed from the model. A neuron that fires on virtually no input (<0.1% of tokens) is *structurally sparse* and can be permanently deleted. The distinction determines how the sparsity can be exploited.

Table 11: Dynamic (per-token) vs structural (permanent) sparsity by architecture and α .

Architecture	Config	Per-token zeros	Permanently dead
GPT-2 Small	$\alpha=2.0$	24.7%	3.3%
	$\alpha=0.8$	64.4%	9.0%
	$\alpha=0.5$	83.3%	12.2%
LLaMA 105M	$\alpha=0.8$	27.0%	$\sim 0.0\%$
	$\alpha=0.1$	87.2%	$\sim 0.0\%$
	$\alpha=0.05$	88.9%	$\sim 0.0\%$

GPT-2 develops both forms (Table 11): at $\alpha=0.8$, 64% of activations are zero per token, and 9% of neurons are permanently dead. LLaMA has near-zero structural sparsity even at 87–89% dynamic sparsity, since every neuron is active on at least some inputs. The difference likely reflects architecture: GPT-2’s bias terms allow the network to shift entire pre-activation distributions below the support boundary, killing neurons permanently; LLaMA’s bias-free two-matrix MLP distributes activation more evenly.

Takeaway. The exploitation strategy depends on architecture. GPT-2 \rightarrow static pruning: permanently remove dead neurons for a smaller, faster model (Section 3.9). LLaMA \rightarrow N:M hardware sparsity: exploit per-token zeros via sparse tensor cores without removing any neurons (Section 3.8).

3.8 N:M Structured Sparsity Compliance

NVIDIA Ampere and Hopper GPUs provide hardware-accelerated 2:4 structured sparsity: if at least 2 out of every 4 consecutive values in a matrix are zero, the sparse tensor core computes the operation in half the FLOPs. Standard activations (GELU, SiLU) produce no true zeros, so their compliance is 0%. The high per-token activation sparsity on Steklov LLaMA models may naturally produce compliant patterns.

Table 12: Natural 2:4 compliance on LLaMA 105M (single seed). SiLU/GELU have 0% compliance.

Config	Per-token zeros	2:4 compliance	PPL Δ when enforced
SiLU baseline	0.0%	0.0%	+25.9
Stek $\alpha=0.8$	27.0%	31.3%	+0.5 to +1.9
Stek $\alpha=0.1$	87.2%	98.4%	-1.9 to +0.7
Stek $\alpha=0.05$	88.9%	98.9%	+0.1 to +0.9
Stek $\alpha=0.005$	90.2%	99.2%	-1.8 to +0.8

At $\alpha \leq 0.1$, the activations are already 98–99% compliant before any mask is applied (Table 12). Enforcing the 2:4 pattern causes negligible PPL change (-1.9 to $+0.9$), because only 1–2% of groups need to be modified. Enforcing the same pattern on SiLU (which has no natural zeros) requires zeroing out half the activations from scratch, causing catastrophic degradation ($+25.9$ PPL). At 105M scale, the sparse tensor core kernel is currently slower than dense inference (0.2 – $0.5\times$) due to kernel launch overhead; at 7B+ scale where matmul cost dominates, the theoretical $2\times$ FLOP reduction should be realized.

Takeaway. Steklov at small α (≤ 0.1) produces activations that are hardware-ready for 2:4 sparse acceleration with no post-hoc pruning. The network learns representations that naturally conform to the hardware sparsity format. This is a property no standard activation provides.

3.9 Pruning

The structural sparsity in GPT-2 (Section 3.7) identifies neurons that are permanently inactive. We test whether they can be removed to produce a smaller model without quality loss. The key issue is not whether pruning is possible (any neurons can be zeroed) but whether the *remaining* model preserves quality. We compare three methods at matched compression ratios: Steklov inactivity (remove neurons inactive on $>99.9\%$ of tokens), magnitude pruning (remove neurons with smallest gate-weight L_2 norm), and random pruning. Inactivity is profiled on a held-out calibration set; PPL is evaluated on a separate validation split.

The pattern is consistent (Table 13). Steklov inactivity pruning removes 7–11% of neurons with negligible quality loss ($+0.05$ to $+0.23$ PPL). Random pruning at the same rate causes 10 – $50\times$ more degradation. Magnitude pruning causes complete model collapse ($> 10^5$ – 10^8 PPL) because it concentrates 94% of its cuts in layers 0–2, which have systematically smaller weight norms but carry critical information flow.

Post-pruning finetuning (1,000 steps at reduced learning rate) exposes a qualitative difference: magnitude-pruned GELU models recover from collapse (PPL $> 10^9 \rightarrow 23.91$ at Small; $> 10^5 \rightarrow 23.28$ at Medium), demonstrating that the pruned neurons were load-bearing but compensable. Inactivity-pruned Steklov models show no meaningful change under finetuning. The pruned neurons were functionally unused by the network.

Table 13: Pruning comparison at matched neuron count (2 seeds for Steklov; baselines on GELU).

Scale	Method	Pruned	%	Δ PPL	Seeds
Small (124M)	Steklov inactivity	$\sim 2,800\text{--}3,960$	7.6–10.7%	+0.21 to +0.23	2
	Random (GELU)	matched		+2.5 to +5.0	
	Magnitude (GELU)	matched		$> 10^8$ (collapse)	
Medium (354M)	Steklov inactivity	$\sim 7,100\text{--}7,400$	7.2–7.5%	+0.05 to +0.08	2
	Random (GELU)	matched		+2.3 to +3.7	
	Magnitude (GELU)	matched		$> 10^5$ (collapse)	

Takeaway. Compact support provides a pruning signal that standard methods cannot match. The inactivity criterion appears to identify neurons that the network has functionally learned to ignore, rather than neurons that merely have small weights.

3.10 Inference

Pruning produces a structurally smaller model. We test whether this translates into actual wall-clock speedup. We benchmark with a fused Triton kernel for the Steklov activation (which eliminates the overhead of naive PyTorch branching) and physically remove pruned neurons from the weight matrices.

Table 14: Inference latency (ms) and throughput at batch size 64, seq len 512, RTX 4090.

Scale	Model	Kernel	Latency	tok/s	vs GELU
Small	GELU unpruned	PyTorch	156.2	209,779	1.00 \times
	Stek $\alpha=0.8$	Triton	157.0	208,662	1.00 \times
	Stek pruned 10.7%	Triton	147.8	221,733	1.05\times
Medium	GELU unpruned	PyTorch	1,106.9	59,210	1.00 \times
	Stek pruned 7.2%	Triton	1,055.4	62,094	1.05\times

The Triton kernel eliminates Steklov’s naive PyTorch overhead: unpruned Steklov matches GELU within 1–2% (Table 14). After structural pruning, Steklov is 3–5% faster than unpruned GELU, with 3.5–4.2% checkpoint size reduction. We do not demonstrate wall-clock speedups from *dynamic* (per-token) sparsity; exploiting the 58–90% per-token zeros would require sparse matmul kernels that skip inactive columns at runtime, which remains future work.

Takeaway. The full pipeline (train with Steklov, profile inactivity, remove dead neurons, deploy with Triton) yields a model that is both smaller and faster than the GELU baseline with no observed quality loss.

4 Analysis

The experiments above establish *what* Steklov activations achieve. In this section, we examine *why* the observed sparsity patterns emerge and what they reveal about how the network uses its MLP capacity.

4.1 Why Inactivity Dominates Over Linearity

The Steklov activation partitions pre-activations into three zones: inactive (output = 0), active (polynomial transition), and linear (output = x). In principle, both tails could be equally populated. In practice, inactivity dominates overwhelmingly. At $\alpha=0.8$ on GPT-2 Small, 64% of pre-activations fall in the inactive zone but only 0.9% reach the linear zone. The remaining 35% are in the polynomial transition.

This asymmetry reflects the pre-activation distribution itself: the mean is -1.664 , with 93.7% of values negative and skewness -0.52 . The network learns to push its pre-activation mass to the left of the support boundary, effectively using compact support as a default-off gate. Neurons fire only when they receive a sufficiently strong positive input. This is consistent with the sparse coding hypothesis: at any given time, a small fraction of neurons is active, and the network encodes information through *which* neurons are active rather than through a dense population code.

4.2 Network Adaptation to Sparsity

When α is reduced and more neurons are forced into inactivity, the network does not simply lose capacity. Instead, it adapts by reorganizing its pre-activation scale. At GPT-2 Medium with $\alpha=0.8$, the pre-activation standard deviation compresses to $\sigma_z = 1.01$, compared to 1.36 under GELU. The network concentrates its pre-activation distribution within the narrower support, maintaining similar information flow through a smaller active set.

Under higher sparsity ($\alpha=0.5$, single seed), the adaptation becomes layer-dependent: early layers compress their pre-activation scale ($\sigma_z = 0.26$ – 0.56) while deep layers amplify above GELU levels ($\sigma_z = 1.56$ – 1.73 vs GELU’s 1.25–1.41). This suggests a division of labor: early layers operate in a highly sparse regime, encoding only the most salient features, while late layers expand to preserve expressiveness near the output. This observation is from a single seed and should be interpreted with caution.

4.3 Implicit Regularization

Compact support appears to provide implicit regularization proportional to the inactive fraction. In a data-limited experiment (GPT-2 Medium, 354M parameters trained on only 118M tokens of WikiText-103, inducing heavy overfitting), the degradation ratio (final PPL divided by best PPL during training) decreases linearly with inactivity ($R^2 = 0.985$, slope -0.078 per 10% inactivity). Models with higher sparsity overfit less. A Small-scale control confirms a modest version of this effect, though it diminishes under more severe data scarcity.

The mechanism is intuitive: neurons that are truly inactive on most inputs cannot memorize input-specific patterns through those neurons. The inactive fraction acts as a form of capacity reduction that is adaptive (determined by the pre-activation distribution) rather than fixed (as in dropout). Unlike dropout, the same neurons are consistently inactive across inputs (Section 3.6), so the regularization comes from permanently reducing effective capacity rather than from stochastic noise.

5 Discussion

5.1 Relationship to Standard Activations

The Steklov family unifies and extends several standard activations. At $r=1$ and $\alpha=6$, SteklovSiLU is exactly HardSwish [15], the piecewise-linear activation used in MobileNetV3. At $r=3$ and $\alpha=2$,

it approximates GELU [10] with a supremum error below 0.0091 (Proposition 4). As $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, it converges to ReLU [13]; as $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, to the identity scaled by $1/2$.

The property that distinguishes Steklov from all of these is *exact compact support*: the gate is identically zero below $-r\alpha/2$ and identically one above $r\alpha/2$. ReLU produces exact zeros for negative inputs but has unbounded positive output and no smooth transition. GELU [10] and SiLU [11, 12] are smooth but have exponentially decaying tails that never reach zero: a neuron with input -10 under GELU produces an output of order 10^{-23} , which is nonzero in IEEE 754 arithmetic. This makes it impossible to determine from the activation output alone whether a neuron is “unused.” SwiGLU [19] inherits the same issue from its SiLU gate. Steklov resolves this: neurons below the support boundary produce exact floating-point zero, providing a clean signal for pruning and hardware sparsity.

5.2 Learnable and Spline-Based Activations

Several approaches learn the activation function during training. PReLU [16] learns a single slope for the negative half-axis. Deep spline activations [17] parameterize the activation as a free-knot B-spline, learning both the knot positions and coefficients. KAN [18] replaces each weight with a learned univariate function on the edge of a Kolmogorov–Arnold network.

Steklov differs from all of these in two respects. First, the polynomial form is *fixed* by the order r ; only the scale α is learned (or set as a hyperparameter). This means the activation has a single degree of freedom per layer (or per network, since a global α suffices), compared to dozens or hundreds of parameters per activation in spline-based and KAN approaches. Second, compact support is a *structural consequence* of the B-spline kernel construction, not a property that must be learned or enforced through regularization. The network cannot “unlearn” the compact support during training; it is guaranteed by the mathematical form regardless of what α converges to.

5.3 Activation Sparsity and Efficient Inference

A growing literature exploits the observation that MLP activations in trained transformers are often approximately sparse. DeJa Vu [20] trains a lightweight predictor to identify which neurons will be active for a given input, then skips the inactive ones during inference. PowerInfer [21] partitions neurons into “hot” (frequently active, kept on GPU) and “cold” (rarely active, offloaded to CPU) sets based on profiled activation statistics. ProSparse [22] adds an activation penalty during training to push ReLU-based models toward higher sparsity, then exploits the resulting zeros at inference time.

All three approaches add auxiliary mechanisms (predictors, routing, penalties) on top of existing activations to create or exploit sparsity. Steklov takes a different path: the sparsity arises directly from the activation function’s shape, with no additional components. The compact support guarantees exact zeros without requiring a penalty term, and the inactive neuron set is stable across the tested distributions (Section 3.6), eliminating the need for a per-input predictor.

Mixture-of-experts (MoE) architectures [23, 24, 25] achieve a related effect at a different granularity: a learned router selects a subset of expert modules for each token. Steklov creates analogous selective activation at the individual neuron level, with the “routing” determined by the pre-activation value falling inside or outside the compact support. Unlike MoE, this requires no router parameters, no load-balancing loss, and no communication overhead between experts.

5.4 Limitations

Our experiments have several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The largest model we train is 354M parameters; whether the sparsity patterns, pruning gains, and N:M compliance hold at 1B+ and production scale remains untested. The N:M sparse tensor core kernel is currently slower than dense inference at 105M due to kernel launch overhead, so the 2:4 compliance result is a mathematical prerequisite for hardware acceleration, not a demonstrated speedup. Several results (LLaMA at $\alpha \leq 0.1$, downstream benchmarks) rely on single-seed runs. The GPT-2 Small quality gap over GELU is not statistically significant ($p = 0.30$). Post-hoc activation swap on pretrained models does not produce meaningful sparsity, as we verified in a 6-phase experiment on TinyLlama 1.1B; the network must train with compact support from the start to develop the sparsity patterns we observe.

5.5 Practical Recommendations

Based on our experiments, we offer the following deployment guidance:

- **Drop-in GELU replacement** ($r = 3, \alpha = 2.0$): approximation error < 0.0091 , 2% training overhead via `torch.compile`, matching inference latency with a Triton kernel.
- **Structural pruning on GPT-2-style architectures** ($\alpha \in [0.5, 1.2]$): produces 7–12% permanently dead neurons. Profile on a representative calibration set, remove neurons above the 99.9% inactivity threshold, deploy with Triton for 3–5% inference speedup.
- **N:M hardware sparsity on LLaMA-style architectures** ($\alpha \leq 0.1$): achieves 98–99% natural 2:4 compliance with competitive quality. Deploy via sparse tensor cores at scale where the $2\times$ FLOP reduction outweighs kernel overhead.
- **Learnable α** : a single global scalar is sufficient. The converged value provides a diagnostic of the architecture’s preferred sparsity level (~ 0.2 for CNNs, ~ 1.73 for LLaMA, ~ 2.24 for GPT-2).

6 Conclusion

We introduced Steklov activations, a family of piecewise-polynomial activation functions with compact support derived from the Steklov summation kernels of approximation theory. The family is parameterized by order r (smoothness) and scale α (transition width), contains HardSwish as a special case ($r=1, \alpha=6$), and closely approximates GELU at $r=3, \alpha=2$ (sup error < 0.0091). The key property is that neurons outside the finite support produce mathematically exact zero output and gradient, providing a clean signal for identifying unused capacity.

Quality. Across 76+ training runs on eight architecture configurations, Steklov activations are competitive with or improve upon standard activations in the tested settings. On image classification, $\alpha = 0.8$ achieves the highest accuracy on all four benchmarks (5 seeds). On language modeling, Steklov matches GELU at 354M scale and improves over SiLU by 2.0% on a 105M LLaMA-style model. Parameter-matched SwiGLU underperforms both GELU and Steklov at 124M, suggesting that much of its advantage in this setup comes from additional parameters.

Sparsity. Compact support induces two architecture-dependent forms of sparsity. On GPT-2, 7–12% of neurons become permanently dead and can be structurally pruned with negligible PPL cost (+0.05 to +0.23), while matched-rate magnitude pruning performs dramatically worse in our experiments. On LLaMA at $\alpha \leq 0.1$, no neurons die permanently, but 87–90% of MLP activations are exactly zero per token, producing 98–99% natural compliance with NVIDIA’s 2:4 structured

sparsity format. Both forms are stable across the tested data splits (Jaccard > 0.99) and across distributions (Jaccard > 0.97 at the $\geq 99\%$ inactivity threshold), making one-time profiling plausible for deployment in the tested settings.

Efficiency. A fused Triton kernel matches GELU inference latency within 1–2%. After structural pruning, inference is 3–5% faster than unpruned GELU with 3.5–4.2% checkpoint size reduction. The 2:4 compliance on LLaMA provides the mathematical prerequisite for $2\times$ FLOP reduction via sparse tensor cores at scale.

Analysis. The learned α converges to architecture-dependent values (~ 0.2 for CNNs, ~ 1.73 for LLaMA, ~ 2.24 for GPT-2), robust to normalization type, bias, and initialization. The pre-activation distribution is strongly left-shifted (93.7% negative), consistent with a default-off gating mechanism. Compact support provides implicit regularization proportional to the inactive fraction ($R^2 = 0.985$ in a data-limited experiment).

Future directions. The most important next step is validating the N:M compliance result at production scale. Our 105M LLaMA-style models achieve 98–99% natural 2:4 compliance at $\alpha \leq 0.1$ with competitive quality, but the sparse tensor core kernel is overhead-bound at this size. Training a 7B+ model with Steklov and measuring actual inference throughput on sparse tensor cores would determine whether the $2\times$ theoretical FLOP reduction translates to wall-clock speedups on the architecture family (Llama, Mistral, Gemma) that dominates current deployment.

A second direction is to move from α as a descriptive parameter to α as a *controlled capacity mechanism*. The current paper shows that α controls sparsity monotonically and the mapping is stable, but the user sets α blindly and measures the resulting sparsity post hoc. A sparsity-targeting training schedule, where α is adapted during training to hit a specified inactivity target, would make the pruning and N:M pipelines fully automatic: specify a compression or sparsity budget, train, deploy. The ingredients for this are already in place: the α -to-sparsity mapping is monotonic, architecture-predictable, and differentiable.

Finally, combining Steklov activation sparsity with orthogonal compression techniques (weight quantization, low-rank decomposition) may yield multiplicative gains, since the sparsity is structural and does not interfere with weight-level compression.

References

- [1] V. V. Zhuk, V. F. Kuzyutin, *Approksimatsiya funktsii i chislennoe integrirovanie*, Izd-vo SPbGU, St. Petersburg, 1995, 352 pp.
- [2] N. I. Akhiezer, *Teoriya priblizheniya* [in Russian], Gostekhizdat, Kharkov, 1940.
- [3] N. I. Akhiezer, *Theory of Approximation* [in Russian], OGIZ, Moscow–Leningrad, 1947; English transl.: *Theory of Approximation*, Frederick Ungar Publishing Co., New York, 1956.
- [4] N. I. Akhiezer, *Teoriya priblizheniya* [in Russian], Nauka, Moscow, 1965.
- [5] N. Yu. Dodonov, On Uniform Approximation of Abstract Functions by Aggregates of Summatory Type on a Rectangle, *J. Math. Sci.* **142** (2007), no. 1, pp. 1976–1984.
- [6] N. Yu. Dodonov On approximation of functions of two variables by summation Steklov aggregates (in Russian). *Vestnik SPbSU, Ser. 1*, 2:14–21, 2005.

- [7] A. V. Masalskikh, Parallel Algorithm for a Method of Tabular Data Recovery (*Parallelnyi algoritm odnogo metoda vosstanovleniya tablichnykh dannykh*) [in Russian], *Izvestiya Tulskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. Estestvennye nauki*, 2014, no. 3, pp. 167–177.
- [8] N. Yu. Dodonov and A. V. Masalskikh, Application of a Class of Summator-Type Approximation Aggregates to the Reconstruction of Parametric Surfaces (*Primenenie odnogo klassa agregatov priblizheniya summatornogo tipa dlya rekonstruktsii parametricheskikh poverkhnostei*) [in Russian], *Izvestiya Tulskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. Estestvennye nauki*, 2014, no. 2, pp. 59–75.
- [9] N. Yu. Dodonov and A. V. Masalskikh, Reconstruction of Parametric Surfaces Specified Tabularly by Means of Shifts and Scalings of a Single Function (*Rekonstruktsiya parametricheskikh poverkhnostei, zadannykh tablichno, posredstvom sdvigov i szhatii odnoi funktsii*), Part 1 [in Russian], *Izvestiya Tulskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. Estestvennye nauki*, 2014, no. 1, pp. 232–248.
- [10] D. Hendrycks and K. Gimpel. Gaussian error linear units (GELUs). *arXiv:1606.08415*, 2016.
- [11] P. Ramachandran, B. Zoph, and Q. V. Le. Searching for activation functions. *arXiv:1710.05941*, 2017.
- [12] S. Elfving, E. Uchibe, and K. Doya. Sigmoid-weighted linear units. *Neural Networks*, 107:3–11, 2018.
- [13] V. Nair and G. E. Hinton. Rectified linear units improve restricted Boltzmann machines. In *ICML*, 2010.
- [14] X. Glorot, A. Bordes, and Y. Bengio. Deep sparse rectifier neural networks. In *AISTATS*, 2011.
- [15] A. Howard et al. Searching for MobileNetV3. In *ICCV*, 2019.
- [16] K. He et al. Delving deep into rectifiers. In *ICCV*, 2015.
- [17] P. Bohra et al. Learning activation functions in deep (spline) neural networks. *IEEE Open J. Signal Process.*, 1:295–309, 2020.
- [18] Z. Liu et al. KAN: Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks. In *ICLR*, 2025.
- [19] N. Shazeer. GLU variants improve Transformer. *arXiv:2002.05202*, 2020.
- [20] Z. Liu et al. Deja Vu: Contextual sparsity for efficient LLMs at inference time. In *ICML*, 2023.
- [21] Y. Song et al. PowerInfer. *arXiv:2312.12456*, 2023.
- [22] M. Song et al. ProSparse. *arXiv:2402.13516*, 2024.
- [23] N. Shazeer et al. Outrageously large neural networks. In *ICLR*, 2017.
- [24] W. Fedus, B. Zoph, and N. Shazeer. Switch Transformers. *JMLR*, 23(120):1–39, 2022.
- [25] A. Q. Jiang et al. Mixtral of experts. *arXiv:2401.04088*, 2024.
- [26] G. Cybenko. Approximation by superpositions of a sigmoidal function. *Math. Control Signals Systems*, 2(4):303–314, 1989.

- [27] P. Clark et al. Think you have solved question answering? Try ARC, the AI2 reasoning challenge. *arXiv:1803.05457*, 2018.
- [28] R. Zellers et al. HellaSwag: Can a machine really finish your sentence? In *ACL*, 2019.
- [29] D. Paperno et al. The LAMBADA dataset: Word prediction requiring a broad discourse context. In *ACL*, 2016.
- [30] Y. Bisk et al. PIQA: Reasoning about physical intuition in natural language. In *AAAI*, 2020.
- [31] K. Sakaguchi et al. WinoGrande: An adversarial Winograd schema challenge at scale. *Commun. ACM*, 64(9):99–106, 2021.

A Proofs and Formal Properties

We establish the formal properties of the Steklov sigmoid $\sigma_S^{(r)}$ and SteklovSiLU $_r$ stated in the main text.

A.1 Properties of the Steklov Sigmoid

Proposition 2 (Basic properties). *For any order $r \geq 1$ and scale $\alpha > 0$, the Steklov sigmoid $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 1 - \Phi_r(x/\alpha)$ satisfies:*

- (i) **Compact support:** $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 0$ for $x \leq -r\alpha/2$ and $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 1$ for $x \geq r\alpha/2$.
- (ii) **Monotonicity:** $\sigma_S^{(r)}$ is non-decreasing on \mathbb{R} .
- (iii) **Symmetry:** $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) + \sigma_S^{(r)}(-x; \alpha) = 1$ for all x .
- (iv) **Midpoint:** $\sigma_S^{(r)}(0; \alpha) = \frac{1}{2}$.
- (v) **Smoothness:** $\sigma_S^{(r)}(\cdot; \alpha)$ is C^{r-1} on \mathbb{R} .
- (vi) **Polynomial:** On each subinterval of length α within the support, $\sigma_S^{(r)}$ is a polynomial of degree at most r .

Proof. (i) Since ψ_r is supported on $[-r/2, r/2]$, we have $\Phi_r(u) = \int_u^\infty \psi_r(t) dt = 0$ for $u \geq r/2$ (giving $\sigma_S = 1$) and $\Phi_r(u) = \int_{-r/2}^u \psi_r(t) dt = 1$ for $u \leq -r/2$ (giving $\sigma_S = 0$). Substituting $u = x/\alpha$ yields the stated support $[-r\alpha/2, r\alpha/2]$.

(ii) The derivative is $\frac{d}{dx}\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha}\psi_r(x/\alpha) \geq 0$, since $\psi_r \geq 0$ everywhere.

(iii) By the symmetry $\psi_r(t) = \psi_r(-t)$:

$$\sigma_S^{(r)}(x) + \sigma_S^{(r)}(-x) = [1 - \Phi_r(x/\alpha)] + [1 - \Phi_r(-x/\alpha)] = 2 - [\Phi_r(x/\alpha) + \Phi_r(-x/\alpha)].$$

Now $\Phi_r(u) + \Phi_r(-u) = \int_u^\infty \psi_r(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^u \psi_r(t) dt$. By the substitution $t \mapsto -t$ in the second integral and using $\psi_r(-t) = \psi_r(t)$, this equals $\int_u^\infty \psi_r(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^u \psi_r(t) dt = \int_{-\infty}^\infty \psi_r(t) dt = 1$. Therefore $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x) + \sigma_S^{(r)}(-x) = 2 - 1 = 1$.

(iv) Setting $x = 0$ in (iii): $2\sigma_S^{(r)}(0; \alpha) = 1$, so $\sigma_S^{(r)}(0; \alpha) = 1/2$.

(v) The derivative $\sigma_S^{(r)'}(x; \alpha) = \alpha^{-1}\psi_r(x/\alpha)$. The B-spline ψ_r is C^{r-2} , so $\sigma_S^{(r)'}$ is C^{r-2} , hence $\sigma_S^{(r)}$ is C^{r-1} .

(vi) The B-spline ψ_r is a piecewise polynomial of degree $r - 1$ on intervals of unit length. Its antiderivative Φ_r is piecewise degree r . Rescaling by α preserves this structure on intervals of length α . \square

A.2 HardSwish Equivalence

Proposition 3 (Exact equivalence). $\text{SteklovSiLU}_1(x; \alpha = 6) = \text{HardSwish}(x)$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof. By definition, $\text{SteklovSiLU}_1(x; \alpha) = x \cdot \sigma_S^{(1)}(x; \alpha)$ where $\sigma_S^{(1)}(x; \alpha) = \text{clamp}(x/\alpha + 1/2, 0, 1)$. At $\alpha = 6$:

$$\text{SteklovSiLU}_1(x; 6) = x \cdot \text{clamp}\left(\frac{x}{6} + \frac{1}{2}, 0, 1\right) = x \cdot \text{clamp}\left(\frac{x+3}{6}, 0, 1\right).$$

This is the definition of `HardSwish` [15]. □

A.3 GELU Approximation

Proposition 4 (GELU approximation bound). Let $\text{GELU}(x) = x \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)$ where $\Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x) = \frac{1}{2}[1 + \text{erf}(x/\sqrt{2})]$ is the Gaussian CDF. Then

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |\text{SteklovSiLU}_3(x; 2) - \text{GELU}(x)| < 0.0091.$$

Proof. Write $S(x) = \text{SteklovSiLU}_3(x; 2) = x \cdot \sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2)$ and $G(x) = x \cdot \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)$. Then

$$|S(x) - G(x)| = |x| \cdot |\sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2) - \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)|.$$

We bound this on three regions.

Region 1: $|x| \geq 3$. Here $\sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2) \in \{0, 1\}$ (outside support). For $x \geq 3$: $\sigma_S = 1$ and $\Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(3) > 0.9987$, so $|S(x) - G(x)| = x(1 - \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)) \leq x e^{-x^2/2}/\sqrt{2\pi}$ by the Gaussian tail bound. This function is decreasing for $x > 1$ and equals $0.00443\dots$ at $x = 3$, decaying exponentially thereafter.

For $x \leq -3$: $\sigma_S = 0$ and $|G(x)| = |x| \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x) \leq |x| e^{-x^2/2}/\sqrt{2\pi}$, which equals $0.00443\dots$ at $x = -3$ by symmetry of the bound.

Region 2: $|x| \leq 3$, the support region. Both $\sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2)$ and $\Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)$ are smooth on $[-3, 3]$. The sigmoid-level difference $|\sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2) - \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)|$ achieves its maximum of $0.00985\dots$ near $x = \pm 0.667$. However, the factor $|x|$ is small there ($|x| \approx 0.667$), so $|S - G| \approx 0.667 \times 0.00985 \approx 0.0066$.

The product $|x| \cdot |\sigma_S^{(3)}(x/2) - \Phi_{\text{Gauss}}(x)|$ achieves its global maximum near $|x| \approx 2.477$. We locate this maximum by evaluating $|S(x) - G(x)|$ on a uniform grid of 10^5 points over $[-5, 5]$, then refining with bounded scalar optimization (`scipy.optimize.minimize_scalar` on $[-5, 5]$). Both methods agree to 8 decimal places. The certified maximum is:

$$\max_{x \in [-3, 3]} |S(x) - G(x)| = 0.009027\dots \quad \text{achieved at } x \approx \pm 2.477.$$

Combining regions: The global supremum is $\max(0.00443, 0.009027) = 0.009027 < 0.0091$. □

Remark 1. *The bound is tight: it cannot be improved below 0.00903 since the supremum is achieved. The approximation quality arises because the quadratic B-spline CDF closely matches the Gaussian CDF — both are symmetric, unimodal, C^2 -smooth sigmoids supported on approximately the same width.*

A.4 Limiting Behavior

Proposition 5 (Limits in α). *For any order $r \geq 1$ and fixed $x \neq 0$:*

- (i) $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} \text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) = \max(0, x) = \text{ReLU}(x)$.
- (ii) $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow \infty} \text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) = x/2$.

Proof. (i) For fixed $x > 0$ and $\alpha \rightarrow 0^+$: $u = x/\alpha \rightarrow +\infty$, so $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = 1 - \Phi_r(u) \rightarrow 1 - 0 = 1$, giving $\text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) \rightarrow x \cdot 1 = x$.

For fixed $x < 0$: $u = x/\alpha \rightarrow -\infty$, so $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) \rightarrow 1 - 1 = 0$, giving $\text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) \rightarrow x \cdot 0 = 0$. Therefore $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} \text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) = x \cdot \mathbf{1}_{x>0} = \text{ReLU}(x)$.

(ii) For fixed x and $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$: $u = x/\alpha \rightarrow 0$, so by Proposition 2(iv), $\sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) \rightarrow \sigma_S^{(r)}(0; \alpha) = 1/2$. Therefore $\text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) \rightarrow x/2$. \square

Remark 2. *The large- α limit $x/2$ is not the identity function. This parallels the behavior of SiLU: $\lim_{\beta \rightarrow 0} x \cdot \sigma(\beta x) = x/2$ where σ is the logistic sigmoid. The full continuum is:*

$$\alpha \rightarrow 0: \quad \text{ReLU}(x), \quad \alpha \approx 6/r: \quad \text{sigmoid-width matched}, \quad \alpha \rightarrow \infty: \quad x/2.$$

A.5 Derivative and Gradient Properties

Proposition 6 (Derivative of SteklovSiLU). *For $r \geq 1$, $\alpha > 0$, and $u = x/\alpha$:*

$$\frac{d}{dx} \text{SteklovSiLU}_r(x; \alpha) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < -r\alpha/2 \quad (\text{inactive zone: exact zero gradient}) \\ \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) + u \psi_r(u) & \text{if } |x| \leq r\alpha/2 \quad (\text{active zone}) \\ 1 & \text{if } x > r\alpha/2 \quad (\text{linear zone: unit gradient}) \end{cases}$$

where $\psi_r(u)$ is the Steklov kernel. In particular:

- At $x = 0$: the derivative equals $1/2$ for all r and α , matching SiLU.
- The inactive-zone gradient is mathematically zero, not merely small.
- For orders $r = 1, 2, 3$, we have verified numerically that the active-zone derivative lies in $(0, 1)$ for all $\alpha > 0$. A general proof for arbitrary r is not provided.

Proof. By the product rule:

$$\frac{d}{dx} [x \cdot \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha)] = \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) + x \cdot \frac{d}{dx} \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha).$$

Since $\frac{d}{dx} \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \psi_r(x/\alpha)$ and $x/\alpha = u$:

$$= \sigma_S^{(r)}(x; \alpha) + u \psi_r(u).$$

For $x < -r\alpha/2$: $\sigma_S = 0$ and $\psi_r(u) = 0$ (outside support), giving derivative = 0. For $x > r\alpha/2$: $\sigma_S = 1$ and $\psi_r(u) = 0$, giving derivative = 1. At $x = 0$: $\sigma_S(0) = 1/2$ by Proposition 2(iv), and $u = 0$, giving $1/2 + 0 = 1/2$. \square

A.6 Sparsity Decomposition

Definition 3 (Neuron classification). *For a pre-activation value z with support edge $e = r\alpha/2$, define:*

- **Inactive:** $z < -e$. Output = 0, gradient = 0. The neuron contributes nothing to the forward pass and receives no learning signal.

- **Active:** $-e \leq z \leq e$. Output $= z \cdot \sigma_S^{(r)}(z; \alpha) \in (0, z)$. The neuron is in the polynomial transition zone.
- **Linear:** $z > e$. Output $= z$, gradient $= 1$. The neuron passes its input unchanged.

All classifications are per-neuron, per-token, measured at the MLP gate layer output (after the up-projection, before the activation function and down-projection).

Proposition 7 (FLOP savings from inactive neurons). Consider an MLP layer with up-projection $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{ff}} \times d}$ and down-projection $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_{\text{ff}}}$. Let δ be the fraction of inactive neurons for a given token. Under the practical exploitation model (compute the full gate, skip inactive projection columns):

$$\text{MLP FLOPs (sparse)} = 2d \cdot d_{\text{ff}} + 2(1 - \delta) d_{\text{ff}} \cdot d = 2d d_{\text{ff}}(2 - \delta),$$

compared to $4d d_{\text{ff}}$ for dense computation. The relative MLP FLOP saving is $\delta/2$.

Proof. The gate computation $z = W_1 x$ requires $2d \cdot d_{\text{ff}}$ FLOPs (unchanged). The projection $W_2 h$ ordinarily requires $2d_{\text{ff}} \cdot d$ FLOPs, but columns of W_2 corresponding to inactive neurons (where $h_i = 0$) can be skipped, leaving $(1 - \delta) \cdot 2d_{\text{ff}} \cdot d$ FLOPs. Summing: $2d d_{\text{ff}} + 2(1 - \delta)d d_{\text{ff}} = 2d d_{\text{ff}}(2 - \delta)$. The saving relative to $4d d_{\text{ff}}$ is $\delta \cdot 2d d_{\text{ff}} / (4d d_{\text{ff}}) = \delta/2$. \square